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SHAPING THE FUTURE OF ENDODONTICS AND RESTORATIVE CARE

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Aims & Scope

Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry (*J Endod Restor Dent*) is a highly respected scientific journal that caters to the needs of those interested in the fields of endodontics and restorative dentistry. This online-only journal follows a rigorous and independent peer-review process, ensuring that all articles are unbiased and of the highest quality. The double-blinded approach employed by Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry further strengthens its credibility, making it a trusted source of information for researchers, practitioners, and students alike. With its biannual release schedule, readers can look forward to two new issues each year, in March and September. Overall, Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest developments in these important areas of dental science.

Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry provides extensive coverage of both clinical and experimental studies on all aspects of endodontics and restorative dentistry. Notably, the journal features original articles, reviews on current topics, case reports, editorial comments, and letters to the editor that follow ethical guidelines. It is important to note that the journal is published solely in English, ensuring it maintains a global reach and fosters international collaboration within the field.

The journal's editorial and publication processes are meticulously designed to meet the highest standards of integrity and quality. To ensure this, the journal adheres to the guidelines set by several reputable organizations such as the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), World Association of Medical Editors (WAME), Council of Science Editors (CSE), Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), European Association of Science Editors (EASE), and National Information Standards Organization (NISO). Furthermore, the journal is committed to upholding the Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing, which have been laid out by the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) at doaj.org/bestpractice.

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Editorial

Welcome Message from the New Editor-in-Chief

 Nessrin A. Taha ^a

^a Editor-in-chief, Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry

KEY WORDS

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ABSTRACT

This editorial marks the beginning of a new chapter for the Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry under the leadership of the new Editor-in-Chief. The journal, established in 2023, has made significant contributions to the field through high-quality research and global collaborations. Looking ahead, the vision includes expanding the journal's scope to emerging areas such as digital dentistry and artificial intelligence, strengthening international contributions, maintaining rigorous peer review standards, and enhancing its impact and visibility. Researchers, clinicians, and academicians are encouraged to contribute to advancing dental science and patient care.

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Welcome Message from the New Editor-in-Chief

It is with great enthusiasm and a deep sense of responsibility that I assume the role of Editor-in-Chief of the Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry. This journal has established itself as a reputable platform for advancing knowledge in endodontics, restorative dentistry, and interdisciplinary dental sciences, and I am honored to continue its legacy.

About the Journal's Legacy

Since its inception in 2023, the Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry has been at the forefront of advancing the science and practice of dental care. Over the years, we have published four issues, showcasing cutting-edge research, innovative clinical findings, and groundbreaking studies that have shaped the field. As Editor-in-Chief, I am committed to continuing this tradition while driving the journal toward new horizons.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Assoc. Prof. Ömer Hatipoğlu for his outstanding leadership and dedication to the journal. Under his guidance, the journal has made significant strides in publishing high-quality research, fostering international collaborations, and maintaining rigorous editorial standards. His commitment and contributions have been invaluable, and I look forward to building upon the strong foundation he has established.

As a clinician, researcher, and academic with a passion for vital pulp therapy, regenerative endodontics, and dental biomaterials, I recognize the importance of bridging the gap between scientific research and clinical practice. The field of endodontics and restorative dentistry is evolving rapidly, and I believe our journal will play a crucial role in shaping the future by publishing innovative, evidence-based research that directly impacts patient care.

Vision for the Future

Looking ahead, my vision for the Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry includes:

- * Expanding the journal's scope to incorporate emerging fields such as digital dentistry, biomaterials, artificial intelligence in endodontics, and minimally invasive restorative techniques.
- * Strengthening global collaborations by encouraging contributions from diverse regions, fostering a truly international exchange of knowledge.
- * Upholding the highest standards of peer review, ensuring that every published study maintains scientific rigor, innovation, and clinical relevance.
- * Enhancing the journal's impact and visibility by advancing its indexing status and promoting interdisciplinary research.

A Call for Collaboration

I cordially invite researchers, clinicians, and academicians to submit their valuable work to our journal. Whether through original research, systematic reviews, clinical trials, or novel methodologies, your contributions are essential to advancing our field.

Furthermore, the success of this journal would not be possible without the dedication of our reviewers, editorial board members, and contributors. I extend my sincere appreciation to all those who invest their time and expertise to ensure the integrity and quality of the research we publish.

As we embark on this new chapter, I welcome your insights, feedback, and collaboration. Together, we will continue to elevate the Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry as a leading voice in dental research and clinical innovation.

Thank you for your continued support and trust in our journal.

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Original Article

Assessment of Pain Scales Used in Endodontic Postoperative Pain Evaluation: Frequency, Advantages, and Limitations

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The study highlights the dominance of VAS and NRS in assessing endodontic postoperative pain. Selecting the appropriate tool improves pain management, enhances patient outcomes, and ensures consistency in research, ultimately standardizing clinical practices.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Postoperative pain is a critical outcome in endodontic research and clinical practice, directly impacting patient satisfaction and treatment success. Various pain assessment tools, such as the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), are employed to quantify and evaluate pain. This study aimed to analyze the frequency of use of different pain assessment tools in endodontic postoperative pain research across different databases.

Materials and Methods: A bibliometric analysis was performed using PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus. The search strategy included commonly used pain scales: VAS, NRS, Heft-Parker Visual Analog Scale, Verbal Rating Scale, Faces Pain Scale, Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire, and Brief Pain Inventory. The results were synthesized to determine the prevalence of these scales in published research.

Results: VAS was the most frequently used tool, with 571 studies in PubMed (75.4%), 581 in Scopus (77.8%), and 346 in Web of Science (74.1%). The NRS followed, with 65 (8.6%), 71 (9.5%), and 51 (10.9%) studies, respectively. Other scales, such as the Heft-Parker Visual Analog Scale, Verbal Rating Scale, and Faces Pain Scale, were used less frequently. Comprehensive tools like the Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire and Brief Pain Inventory had minimal representation.

Conclusion: VAS and NRS dominate endodontic postoperative pain research, reflecting their ease of use and widespread acceptance. Less commonly used tools, while valuable in specific contexts, are underrepresented. Future research should explore the reasons for this disparity and assess the potential of hybrid tools to standardize pain evaluation practices.

1. Introduction

Postoperative pain is a common and significant concern in endodontic treatment, often influencing patient satisfaction and clinical outcomes. The evaluation of pain intensity and its management are critical aspects of clinical practice, as they guide both diagnosis and therapeutic decisions. However, pain is inherently subjective, making its accurate assessment a challenging yet essential task in dentistry.¹

Various pain measurement scales have been developed to quantify pain intensity and characteristics, providing clinicians with tools to evaluate and compare treatment modalities effectively. Among these, the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) is widely recognized and frequently used due to its simplicity and reliability.² Other scales, such as the Numeric Rating Scale (NRS), the McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ), and the Heft-Parker Visual Analog Scale, also play significant roles in assessing pain in both clinical and research settings.³

Endodontic postoperative pain evaluation is particularly complex due to the multifactorial nature of pain perception, which can be influenced by factors such as individual pain thresholds, procedural variables, and the psychological state of the patient.⁴ The selection of an appropriate pain scale is crucial to ensure accurate data collection and meaningful interpretation of pain outcomes.

Despite the widespread use of these scales, there is a lack of comprehensive analysis regarding their application in endodontics. Specifically, it remains unclear which scales are most commonly employed in the literature, their respective strengths and limitations, and their suitability for different clinical scenarios. Addressing this gap is essential to standardize pain assessment in endodontics and enhance the comparability of research

findings.

This study aims to evaluate the frequency of use of different pain scales in endodontic postoperative pain research, describe their methodologies, and discuss their advantages and limitations. By providing a critical overview of these tools, this work seeks to assist clinicians and researchers in selecting the most appropriate scale for their specific needs and contribute to the standardization of pain evaluation in endodontics.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design and Objectives

This study utilized a bibliometric approach to evaluate the frequency and application of pain assessment scales in endodontic postoperative pain research. The objectives were to identify commonly used scales, analyze their distribution across the literature, and discuss their strengths and limitations.

2.2. Literature Search Strategy

A comprehensive search was conducted across three major scientific databases: PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus. For each database, a tailored search query was applied to account for variations in search syntax. The general strategy involved replacing "Visual Analog Scale (VAS)" with other commonly used pain scales to comprehensively capture studies utilizing different methodologies. Details of the advanced queries used in each database are provided in Table 1. The search was iteratively modified for each pain scale. This approach ensured the inclusion of studies using diverse methods for postoperative pain assessment. Screening was completed on the 1st November 2024.

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria required studies to be published in English, involve human participants, assess postoperative pain following endodontic procedures, and use specific pain scales such as VAS, NRS, MPQ, or Heft-Parker. Exclusion criteria included reviews, editorials, and conference abstracts without original data, studies focusing on non-endodontic procedures or experimental animal models, and articles lacking detailed methodology on pain assessment scales.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Jamovi Software (2.3.28) was used for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to determine the frequency of use of each pain scale. Results were presented as percentages and visualized through heat maps and tables.

3. Results

The bibliometric analysis revealed that the VAS was the most frequently used tool for evaluating postoperative pain in endodontic research across all three databases. Specifically, VAS was reported in 571 studies in PubMed (75.4%), 581 studies in Scopus (77.8%), and 346 studies in Web of Science (74.1%), highlighting its dominance as the preferred pain assessment scale (Fig. 1).

The NRS was the second most commonly used scale, with 65 studies in PubMed (8.6%), 71 studies in Scopus (9.5%), and 51 studies in Web of Science (10.9%). This finding reflects the growing preference for simple, numeric-based scales in pain evaluation (Fig. 1).

The Heft-Parker Visual Analog Scale (HP-VAS) also demonstrated a notable presence, with 66 studies in PubMed (8.7%), 48 in Scopus (6.4%), and 34 in Web of Science (7.3%). Although not as widely utilized as VAS or NRS, this scale remains relevant, particularly in studies requiring a modified visual approach to pain assessment (Fig. 1).

Other scales, such as the Verbal Rating Scale (VRS) and the Faces Pain Scale (FPS), showed moderate use. The VRS was identified in 27 studies in PubMed (3.6%), 22 in Scopus (2.9%), and 20 in Web of Science (4.3%). The FPS, often used in pediatric populations, appeared in 24 studies in PubMed (3.2%), 21 in Scopus (2.8%), and 12 in Web of Science (2.6%) (Fig. 1).

Table 1. The used search strategies in information sources

Database	Advanced Search strategy
PubMed	(("root canal instrumentation" OR "root canal retreatment" OR "apexification" OR "endodontic*" OR "root canal*" OR "endodontics") AND ("Visual Analog Scale" OR "VAS"))
Web of Science	TS=(("root canal instrumentation" OR "root canal retreatment" OR "apexification" OR "endodontic*" OR "root canal*" OR "endodontics") AND ("Visual Analog Scale" OR "VAS"))
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(("root canal instrumentation" OR "root canal retreatment" OR "apexification" OR "endodontic*" OR "root canal*" OR "endodontics") AND ("Visual Analog Scale" OR "VAS"))

Less commonly employed scales included the Short-Form McGill Pain Questionnaire (SF-MPQ), with only a few mentions: 3 studies in PubMed (0.4%), 2 in Scopus (0.3%), and 3 in Web of Science (0.6%). Similarly, the Brief Pain Inventory (BPI) and the Pain Intensity Numerical Rating Scale (PI-NRS) were minimally reported, with BPI appearing in just 1 study in Scopus (0.1%) and PI-NRS recorded in only 1 study (0.1%) across all three databases (Fig. 1).

Overall, the findings emphasize a reliance on VAS in endodontic postoperative pain research, while alternative scales remain underutilized despite their potential advantages in specific clinical and demographic contexts.

4. Discussion

Postoperative pain evaluation plays a vital role in understanding and managing patient outcomes in endodontic treatments. It is not only a key determinant of patient satisfaction but also a critical measure of clinical success.^{4,5} In this study, tools like the VAS and NRS emerged as the most commonly utilized methods for assessing pain, reflecting their wide acceptance and practicality. Meanwhile, less frequently used scales, such as the HP-VAS and FPS, demonstrate value in specific clinical scenarios. This discussion aims to critically analyze these pain assessment tools, exploring their strengths, limitations, and applicability across diverse patient populations and clinical contexts. Summary of pain assessment tools used in endodontic postoperative pain measurement was presented in Table 2.

The type of measurement employed by pain assessment scales significantly impacts their effectiveness and suitability in various clinical scenarios. Visual tools, such as the VAS and HP-VAS, rely on patients marking their pain on a visual continuum, which allows

Fig. 1. Heat map of pain scales used in endodontic post-operative pain studies

Table 2. Summary of Pain Assessment Tools Used in Endodontic Postoperative Pain Measurement

Scale Name	Measurement Type	Purpose of Use	Ease of Use	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations	Reliability and Validity	Populations Used	Time of Assessment
Visual Analog Scale (VAS)	Visual	Measures pain intensity	Simple, quick	High sensitivity, widely accepted	Subjective, potential for misinterpretation	Requires patient understanding of scale	High; validated across studies	Adults, general	Immediately, 24-72 hours
Numeric Rating Scale (NRS)	Numeric	Quantifies pain on a 0-10 scale	Very easy	Quick, suitable for broad populations	Limited detail, lacks qualitative data	May miss subtle differences in pain levels	High; reliable in clinical settings	Adults, elderly	Immediately, 24-72 hours
Heft-Parker Visual Analog Scale	Visual	Modified VAS with categories	Moderate	Combines VAS precision with clarity	Less commonly used	Limited to specific studies or contexts	Moderate; validated in specific settings	Adults, pediatrics	Post-procedure
Verbal Rating Scale (VRS)	Verbal	Descriptive pain assessment	Easy, no tools required	Simple for communication	Less precise, subjective descriptions	Cultural/language barriers may impact use	Moderate; less validated	Adults, elderly	Immediately
Faces Pain Scale (FPS)	Visual (Faces)	Pediatric pain evaluation	Simple, child-friendly	Useful for children and non-verbal	Limited for adults, less precision	Suitable only for specific populations	High for pediatrics	Pediatrics, elderly	Immediately, post-procedure
Short-Form McGill Pain (SF-MPQ)	Mixed (Quantitative/Qual.)	Measures pain intensity & quality	Complex, time-consuming	Detailed, multidimensional	Time-consuming, less practical	Limited use in routine clinical practice	High; validated for qualitative data	Chronic pain patients	Long-term follow-up
Brief Pain Inventory (BPI)	Mixed	Evaluates pain severity & impact	Moderate	Measures functional interference	Longer administration time	Limited applicability to acute pain	High; validated for chronic pain	Chronic pain patients	Extended post-procedure
Pain Intensity NRS (PI-NRS)	Numeric	Quantifies pain severity	Very easy	Simplified for quick assessments	Lacks detailed pain information	Limited to numeric severity	High; validated for quick measures	Adults, elderly	Immediately

for nuanced and sensitive measurements. This is particularly advantageous when capturing small changes in pain intensity.⁶ However, visual scales can pose challenges for populations with cognitive impairments, visual limitations, or difficulty understanding abstract concepts, such as elderly patients or those with low health literacy.⁷⁻⁹

In contrast, numeric scales like the NRS and PI-NRS offer simplicity and ease of use by asking patients to directly assign a number to their pain. This makes them particularly suitable for fast-paced clinical settings and broad patient populations.¹⁰ However, these scales may lack the sensitivity to detect subtle differences in pain levels, limiting their utility in research settings where fine gradations in pain are of interest.¹¹ Verbal scales, such as the VRS, offer a categorical approach by using descriptive terms like "mild," "moderate," or "severe." While this is highly accessible and useful for patients unable to engage with visual or numeric scales, the lack of precision and potential for linguistic or cultural interpretation issues can reduce their reliability.¹² Each measurement type thus provides distinct advantages and challenges, and their selection should be guided by the clinical context, patient population, and specific objectives of the assessment.

The intended purpose of pain assessment tools plays a crucial role in determining their appropriateness for specific clinical or research settings. Scales like the VAS and NRS are widely used for their ability to measure pain intensity effectively. These scales are particularly valuable in evaluating the immediate outcomes of interventions, such as the reduction in postoperative pain following endodontic treatments.^{13,14} Their straightforward approach allows clinicians to quickly gauge patient discomfort and make timely decisions regarding pain management strategies.

On the other hand, tools like the SF-MPQ and BPI are designed for more comprehensive pain assessments. These scales not only measure the intensity of pain but also capture its qualitative characteristics, such as the sensory and affective dimensions of the patient's experience.¹⁵ Such detailed assessments are especially useful in research settings or in cases of chronic pain where understanding the multidimensional nature of pain is essential for developing effective treatment plans.

In specific populations, scales like the FPS and VRS are tailored for unique needs. For instance, FPS is highly effective for pediatric patients or individuals with communication difficulties, as it provides a non-verbal method to express pain.¹⁶ Similarly, VRS is often used in situations where simplicity and immediate feedback are prioritized, although its categorical nature may limit its precision.¹⁷ By aligning the choice of pain scale with the intended purpose, clinicians and researchers can ensure more accurate and meaningful pain assessments tailored to their specific objectives.

Despite their widespread use and utility, pain assessment tools are not without limitations, and these must be considered when interpreting their results.¹⁷ The VAS, while highly sensitive to small changes in pain intensity, requires patients to understand and interact with a visual continuum.¹⁸ This reliance on patient comprehension can limit its applicability in populations with cognitive impairments, low literacy, or visual disabilities.¹⁷ Similarly, the NRS, though simple and versatile, may fail to capture the multidimensional nature of pain, reducing its effectiveness in chronic or complex pain scenarios where qualitative insights are necessary.¹⁹

Tools like the VRS and FPS also face challenges. The VRS, for example, relies on predefined categories such as "mild," "moderate," and "severe," which can vary in interpretation based on cultural and linguistic differences. This subjectivity may hinder its reliability in diverse populations. The FPS, while invaluable in pediatric or non-verbal populations, lacks precision and is unsuitable for adult patients or detailed research applications.¹⁷

Comprehensive tools like the SF-MPQ and BPI address many of these limitations by providing detailed, multidimensional assessments. However, their complexity and longer administration times make them impractical for routine clinical use. Additionally, their reliance on patient cooperation and understanding can pose challenges in certain populations.²⁰

Ultimately, no single pain assessment tool is universally applicable. The limitations of each scale highlight the importance of context-specific selection, balancing the need for precision, patient accessibility, and the clinical or research objectives. Addressing these limitations through the development of hybrid or standardized tools could significantly enhance pain evaluation in endodontics and beyond.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the central role of pain assessment tools in endodontic postoperative care, emphasizing their importance in both clinical practice and research. Among the scales analyzed, the VAS and NRS emerged as the most widely used tools, reflecting their simplicity, reliability, and ease of application. However, less commonly utilized scales, such as the HP-VAS and FPS, demonstrate significant value in specific clinical scenarios, such as pediatric or non-verbal patient populations.

The findings underscore the need for clinicians and researchers to align their choice of pain scales with the specific objectives of their evaluations and the demographics of their patient populations. While VAS and NRS remain the dominant tools, comprehensive scales like the SF-MPQ and BPI offer unique

insights in more complex or chronic pain cases, despite their limitations in routine clinical use.

Ultimately, no single pain assessment tool is universally applicable, and the choice should be guided by the clinical context, patient needs, and the nature of the study. Future research should focus on developing hybrid tools that combine the precision, multidimensionality, and practicality required for effective pain assessment. Such advancements could significantly improve pain management and enhance the comparability of findings in endodontic research and beyond.

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Original Article

Orthodontic Anomalies, Dental Caries, and Tooth Loss in Adolescence: Their Impact on Self-Esteem and Body Image: A Cross-Sectional Study

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The study highlights the psychosocial impact of orthodontic treatment needs on body image in adolescents, emphasizing the importance of early orthodontic assessment to enhance self-perception and psychological well-being, ultimately contributing to improved patient outcomes and holistic adolescent care.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to examine the relationship between common dental anomalies, such as orthodontic treatment needs, tooth loss, and dental caries, and their impact on self-esteem and body image in adolescents. Given that adolescence is a critical period for psychological and physical development, understanding how dental health influences these factors is essential.

Materials and Methods: A total of 167 adolescents aged 15–18 years who sought dental care at the Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University Faculty of Dentistry participated in this study. Sociodemographic data, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) scores, and Body Image Scale scores were collected. A clinical oral examination assessed orthodontic treatment needs, tooth loss, and untreated dental caries. Participants were categorized based on their self-esteem and body image scores, and statistical analyses, including Spearman correlation and chi-square tests, were conducted to evaluate associations between dental anomalies, self-esteem, and body image.

Results: A significant negative correlation was found between orthodontic treatment needs and body image ($p = 0.015$), indicating that adolescents requiring orthodontic treatment had lower body image scores. However, no significant relationship was observed between tooth loss, dental caries, and either self-esteem or body image ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: The findings suggest that orthodontic issues are strongly linked to body image concerns in adolescents, whereas tooth loss and dental caries do not appear to significantly affect self-esteem or body image. These results highlight the psychosocial importance of orthodontic treatment and emphasize the need for further longitudinal studies exploring the link between dental health and psychological well-being.

1. Introduction

Self-esteem refers to an individual's positive or negative attitude towards themselves. When a person evaluates themselves positively, their self-esteem is considered high, whereas a negative self-evaluation indicates low self-esteem.¹ Particularly among adolescent girls, self-esteem is closely linked to body image, which is shaped by societal ideals of physical appearance. When individuals perceive themselves as falling short of these ideals, they may develop negative emotions.²

Body image refers to an individual's internalized thoughts and perceptions about their own body and physical appearance. Self-esteem and body image interact dynamically; individuals with a positive perception of their physical appearance tend to exhibit greater confidence and success, whereas those who are dissatisfied with their appearance may experience feelings of insecurity and worthlessness. The physical changes that occur during adolescence, particularly those related to facial aesthetics, can significantly influence body image and self-esteem.³ Given the importance of physical attractiveness in social interactions, orthodontic issues, tooth loss, and dental caries are also relevant factors, as they can contribute to aesthetic concerns and social discomfort. While orthodontic anomalies have been extensively studied in relation to body image, the impact of dental caries and tooth loss remains less explored. These conditions can alter dental appearance, potentially leading to self-consciousness and negative self-perception, making their inclusion in this study essential for a more comprehensive understanding of the psychological effects of dental health on adolescents.⁴

Since self-esteem and body image are psychological constructs and, as previously mentioned, subjective processes, common dental disorders such as orthodontic problems, tooth loss, and

untreated cavities can influence both body image and self-esteem. A limited number of studies have examined the impact of orthodontic treatment needs on body image and self-esteem, with findings indicating that self-esteem tends to improve following orthodontic treatment.⁵

In this context, the present study aims to clearly assess and elucidate the relationship between common dental pathologies and self-esteem and body image during adolescence, a critical developmental period marked by significant physical changes and increased sensitivity to appearance. By doing so, this study seeks to contribute to a better understanding of the psychological impact of dental health on adolescents' self-perception and well-being. Null hypothesis is there is no significant relationship between common dental pathologies (orthodontic anomalies, tooth loss, and dental caries) and self-esteem or body image in adolescents.

2. Materials and Methods

This study was approved by the Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University (Decision No: 2024/224). Written and verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants and parents prior to data collection. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, ensuring the confidentiality and privacy of participants' data.

2.1. Study Design

The study sample consisted of literate adolescents aged 15–18 who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. These individuals applied to the Department of Oral and Dentomaxillofacial Radiology at Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University

Faculty of Dentistry for routine examinations due to various dental complaints. After obtaining informed consent from participants, a routine oral examination was conducted by an oral and dentomaxillofacial radiology specialist to assess common dental anomalies, including the need for orthodontic treatment, permanent tooth loss, fractured teeth, and dental caries.

Following the examination, participants were asked to complete a sociodemographic data form, the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, and the Body Image Scale. The sample was then categorized into two groups based on body image scale cutoff values: those scoring below the cutoff were classified as having low body image, whereas those scoring above the cutoff were classified as having high body image.⁶ These groups were compared in terms of common dental pathologies. Additionally, participants were categorized into high self-esteem (scoring 0–1 on the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale) and low self-esteem (scoring above 1) groups.¹ These groups were also compared in terms of common dental pathologies.

2.2. Indices Used in Oral Examination

a) All maxillary and mandibular anterior teeth, from canine to canine, were examined for traumatic injuries using a modified version of the Ellis classification.⁷

b) The number of missing teeth, their location (maxillary and/or mandibular), and their region (masticatory and/or aesthetic) were assessed. The aesthetic region is defined as the incisors, canines, and first premolars in the maxilla, and the incisors and canines in the mandible. The masticatory region includes the second premolars and the first and second molars in the maxilla, and both premolars and the first and second molars in the mandible.

c) The number, location (maxillary and/or mandibular), and region (masticatory and/or aesthetic) of untreated dentine caries were assessed, secondary caries will not be included.

d) Malocclusion was evaluated using the Index of Orthodontic Treatment Need (IOTN).⁸

The Dental Health Component (DHC) of the IOTN categorizes malocclusions based on various occlusal characteristics into five grades: Grades 1 and 2 indicate little or no need for treatment, Grade 3 represents borderline need, and Grades 4 and 5 signify definite treatment necessity.

2.3. Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES), developed by Morris Rosenberg in 1963,¹ was used in the study to measure self-esteem. After being tested for reliability and validity in the United States, it has been widely used as a measurement tool in various studies. Designed specifically for the adolescent age group, its validity and reliability studies in Turkey were conducted.⁹

RSES consists of 11 subscales and 63 items, assessing self-esteem, continuity of self-concept, trust in others, sensitivity to criticism, depressive affect, daydreaming, perceived threats in interpersonal relationships, ability to engage in discussions, psychological isolation, psychosomatic symptoms, and parental interest. The self-esteem subscale includes ten items, with five measuring positive self-evaluation (items 1, 2, 4, 6, and 7) and five assessing negative self-evaluation (items 3, 5, 8, 9, and 10).¹ Based on the scoring system, self-esteem is categorized as high (0–1 points), moderate (2–4 points), or low (5–6 points). Higher scores indicate lower self-esteem.

2.4. Body Image Scale

The Body Image Scale was developed by Secord and Jourard in 1953⁶ and later validated for reliability and validity by Hovardoglu in 1989.¹⁰ The scale consists of 40 items, each evaluating an organ, body part (such as arms, legs, or face), or bodily function (such as sexual activity level). Participants rate each item on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Dislike" to "Strongly Like". The

total score ranges from 40 to 200, with higher scores indicating greater body satisfaction. The cutoff score for the scale is 135; individuals scoring below this threshold are classified as having low body image.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS 29.0 (IBM, Armonk, USA). The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was applied to assess the normality of variable distributions. Descriptive statistics, including minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, median, frequency, and percentage values, were reported. For categorical variables, the Pearson Chi-Square test was used when the sample size assumption (expected value >5) was met; otherwise, Fisher's Exact test was applied ($p < 0.005$). The relationships between the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, Body Image Scale, tooth loss, dental caries, and the presence of orthodontic problems were analyzed using Spearman correlation analysis ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results

The study included 167 participants, aged between 15 and 17 years, with a median age of 16 years. The height of the participants ranged from 146 cm to 190 cm, with a median height of 165 cm. Their weight varied between 39 kg and 120 kg, with a median weight of 58 kg. Of the participants, 63% ($n=104$) were female and 37% ($n=61$) were male (Table 1).

Regarding education levels, 95% ($n=157$) were high school students, 4.2% ($n=7$) were not attending school, and 1.8% ($n=3$) were university students. The income distribution of the participants' families showed that 23.4% ($n=39$) had an income between 0–17,000 TL, 32.9% ($n=55$) between 17,000–22,000 TL, and 43.7% ($n=73$) had an income of 22,000 TL or more (Table 1).

The educational background of the participants' mothers indicated that 1.8% ($n=3$) were illiterate, 34.1% ($n=57$) had completed primary school, 22.8% ($n=38$) had completed middle school, 29.3% ($n=49$) had completed high school, 10.8% ($n=18$) had a university degree, and 1.2% ($n=2$) had a master's or doctoral degree. The educational background of the fathers showed that 1.2% ($n=2$) were illiterate, 13.8% ($n=23$) had completed primary school, 38.3% ($n=64$) had completed middle school, 29.3% ($n=49$) had completed high school, 13.2% ($n=22$) had a university degree, and 4.2% ($n=7$) had a master's or doctoral degree (Table 1).

According to the Ellis fracture classification, 97.6% ($n=163$) of the participants had no fractures, while 2.4% ($n=4$) had minor fractures. In terms of orthodontic treatment needs, 55.1% ($n=92$) were classified as Grade 1, 19.2% ($n=32$) as Grade 2, 10.2% ($n=17$) as Grade 3, 5.4% ($n=9$) as Grade 4, and 10.2% ($n=17$) as Grade 5 (Table 1).

When evaluating dental caries and tooth loss, 64.1% ($n=107$) of participants had caries in the upper jaw, while 35.9% ($n=60$) did not. In the lower jaw, 59.9% ($n=100$) had caries, whereas 40.1% ($n=67$) had no caries. The prevalence of tooth loss was 10.8% ($n=18$) in both the upper and lower jaws (Table 1).

Regarding psychological assessments, the median RSES score was 1 (range: 0–4.59), while the median Body Image Scale score was 141 (range: 91–193). According to RSES, 39.5% of participants had low self-esteem, while 60.5% had high self-esteem. Similarly, Body Image Scale results showed that 38.3% had low body image, whereas 61.7% had high body image. These findings suggest that, overall, the participants exhibited relatively high levels of self-esteem and body image (Table 1).

A statistically significant relationship was found between body image and the need for orthodontic treatment ($p = 0.015$). However, no statistically significant difference was observed between tooth loss and body image ($p = 0.469$). Similarly, when examining the relationship between dental caries and body image, no significant difference was found ($p = 0.249$) (Table 2).

Table 1. Demographic data of the participants.

Factors	Subgroup	n	[Median (Min-Max)] or %
Age (years)		167	16 (15-17)
Height (cm)		167	165 (146-190)
Weight (kg)		167	58 (39-120)
Gender	Male	61	37%
	Female	104	63%
Income Status of the Family	0-17.000	39	23.4%
	17000-22000	55	32.9%
	22 000 and higher	73	43.7%
Mother's Educational Status	Illiterate	3	1.8%
	Primary school	57	34.1%
	Secondary school	38	22.8%
	High school	49	29.3%
	University	18	10.8%
	Master's or Doctoral Degree	2	1.2%
Father's Educational Status	Illiterate	2	1.2%
	Primary school	23	13.8%
	Secondary school	64	38.3%
	High school	49	29.3%
	University	22	13.2%
	Master's or Doctoral Degree	7	4.2%
Ellis Classification	No Fractures	163	97.6%
	Type 1	4	2.4%
The Need for Orthodontic Treatment	Grade 1	92	55.1%
	Grade 2	32	19.2%
	Grade 3	17	10.2%
	Grade 4	9	5.4%
	Grade 5	17	10.2%
Orthodontic Treatment Need	Present	75	44.9%
	Absent	92	55.1%
Caries in the Maxilla	Present	107	64.1%
	Absent	60	35.9%
Caries in the Mandible	Present	100	59.9%
	Absent	67	40.1%
Dental Caries	Present	40	24%
	Absent	127	76%
Tooth Loss in the Maxilla	Present	18	10.8%
	Absent	149	89.2%
Tooth Loss in the Mandible	Present	18	10.8%
	Absent	149	89.2%
Tooth Loss	Present	27	16.2%
	Absent	140	83.2%
Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale		167	1 (0-4.59)
Body Image Scale		167	141 (91-193)
Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale	Low	66	39.5%
	High	101	60.5%
Body Image Scale	Low	64	38.3%
	High	103	61.7%

N (%), Median (Min-Max)

Table 2. Comparison of Body Image with the Presence of Orthodontic Problems, Tooth Loss, and Dental Caries

		Body Image Scale		
Orthodontic		Low	High	p-value
Treatment Need				
Present	n	36	28	0.015*
Absence	n	39	64	
Tooth Loss				
Present	n	53	87	0.469
Absence	n	11	16	
Dental Caries				
Present	n	51	76	0.249
Absence	n	13	27	

Fisher's Exact Test, * indicates statistical significance

No statistically significant relationship was found between self-esteem and orthodontic problems ($p = 0.517$). Similarly, there was no statistically significant difference between tooth loss and self-esteem ($p = 0.358$). Likewise, the relationship between dental caries and self-esteem was not found to be significant ($p = 0.573$) (Table 3).

According to the Spearman correlation analysis results presented in Fig. 1, a significant negative correlation was found between orthodontic treatment need and body image ($r = -0.180$, $p = 0.010$). However, the effect size indicates that this is a weak correlation, suggesting that while orthodontic treatment need is statistically associated with body image, its actual impact on perception may be limited. This finding suggests that individuals with orthodontic problems may have a more negative body image.

4. Discussion

This study examined the relationship between common dental pathologies and self-esteem and body image in the adolescent age group. The null hypothesis was partially rejected. While no significant relationship was found between tooth loss, dental caries, and self-esteem or body image, the study identified a statistically significant negative correlation between orthodontic treatment needs and body image. These findings suggest that orthodontic concerns are more strongly linked to adolescents' self-perception, whereas tooth loss and dental caries may not significantly impact body image or self-esteem in this age group.

In the present study, 63% of the participants were female adolescents. This may be related to the higher frequency of dental

Table 3. Comparison of the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale with the Presence of Orthodontic Problems, Tooth Loss, and Dental Caries

		Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale		
Orthodontic		Low	High	p-value
Treatment Need				
Present	n	30	45	0.517
Absence	n	36	56	
Tooth Loss				
Present	n	54	86	0.358
Absence	n	12	15	
Dental Caries				
Present	n	51	76	0.249
Absence	n	15	25	

Fisher's Exact Test, * indicates statistical significance

Fig. 1. Spearman Correlation graph comparing Body Image Scale and Orthodontic Treatment Need

visits in females could be explained by hormonal changes affecting dental health, the impact of smile and jaw aesthetics on overall appearance, and greater awareness of oral health among female adolescents.¹¹

When classified according to orthodontic treatment need, 55.1% of the participants were categorized as Grade 1, 19.2% as Grade 2, 10.2% as Grade 3, 5.4% as Grade 4, and 10.2% as Grade 5. Proffit et al.¹² classified the aetiologies of malocclusion into three categories: specific causes, environmental influences, and genetic factors. However, the exact causes remain not fully understood. Regional factors may contribute to the variation in orthodontic treatment needs observed in this study. Additionally, differences between the treatment need rates reported in the literature and those found in this study may be attributed to the inclusion of first-time dental visit patients rather than orthodontic clinic patients and a broader adolescent sample.

This study found a statistically significant relationship between body image and the need for orthodontic treatment. A review of the literature reveals that previous research also supports a strong correlation between orthodontic treatment needs and body image. Aesthetic concerns and social interactions can increase the demand for orthodontic treatment.¹³

In a study conducted by Phillips et al.¹⁴, the impact of dental aesthetics on self-confidence and body image was examined, and it was suggested that dental appearance is a crucial component of body image. Similarly, Klages et al.¹⁵ investigated the effects of orthodontic anomalies on body image and reported that individuals with orthodontic anomalies experienced a negative impact on their body image, while those who underwent orthodontic treatment showed improvement in body perception after treatment.

Research on young adults with malocclusion-related dental aesthetic concerns has explored the impact of these conditions on body image and oral health-related quality of life. Findings suggest that individuals with severe orthodontic issues tend to have a more negative body image, though the psychological effects of these conditions may vary depending on individual perception.¹⁶

Furthermore, a systematic review by Dimberg et al.¹⁷ examined the effects of orthodontic disorders on aesthetic concerns and body image in children and adolescents. The study concluded that orthodontic disorders could increase aesthetic concerns, influencing body image, making the statistically significant association between orthodontic treatment needs and body image an expected finding.

Another study by Sicari et al.¹⁸ found that malocclusion and dental anomalies significantly impact psychological well-being and that orthodontic disorders particularly affect body image negatively in adolescents. The findings of this study, indicating a

relationship between the need for orthodontic treatment and lower body image in adolescents, are consistent with existing literature.

Research investigating the psychological and oral health-related quality of life effects of orthodontic treatment has indicated that individuals who receive orthodontic treatment experience improvements in body image after treatment.¹⁹ The findings of the present study align with previous research demonstrating a negative correlation between orthodontic treatment needs and body image scale scores.

This study found no significant relationship between tooth loss and body image. A review of the literature reveals a lack of studies directly examining the relationship between tooth loss and body image.

However, body image is often defined as a psychological state in which individuals experience intense mental preoccupation with minor or perceived physical imperfections, which can impair functionality and overall quality of life. In existing research, tooth loss has frequently been studied about quality of life, and psychosocial health and body image have been indirectly evaluated through quality-of-life assessments.²⁰

A systematic meta-analysis conducted by Gerritsen et al.²¹ examined the relationship between tooth loss and quality of life, concluding that tooth loss can affect an individual's quality of life and psychosocial well-being. However, its impact on body image may vary depending on factors such as age, the location of tooth loss, and whether the individual uses prosthetics.

Although individuals experiencing tooth loss may be expected to suffer from body image disturbances and decreased self-esteem due to aesthetic concerns and difficulties in social interactions,²² findings from a meta-analysis by Zhang et al.²³ suggest that tooth loss is primarily associated with functional impairments rather than directly affecting body image.

The lack of studies specifically examining the direct relationship between tooth loss and body image, along with the methodological variations in meta-analyses, may contribute to inconsistent findings in the literature. In this context, the absence of a statistically significant relationship between body image and tooth loss in the present study could be explained by the perception of tooth loss as a functional deficiency rather than an aesthetic concern. Additional factors such as the location of the missing tooth and individual differences among participants may also influence these findings.²² Future studies with larger sample sizes and more comprehensive methodologies could provide a deeper understanding of the relationship between body image and tooth loss.

The study found no significant relationship between dental caries and body image. Currently, there are no studies directly examining the impact of dental caries on body image. However, it is thought that dental caries may influence body image and psychosocial well-being by causing both aesthetic and functional issues.

In the literature, dental caries, similar to tooth loss, has often been studied about quality of life, and its potential effects on body image have been discussed indirectly. A study by Kramer et al.²⁴ investigating oral health and quality of life in preschool children reported that dental caries negatively affected the quality of life of both children and their caregivers, particularly in terms of social interactions. However, the study suggested that dental caries might not be a determining factor in an individual's overall body image. Additionally, in adolescents, the duration of a tooth's presence in the mouth is generally shorter compared to adults. Therefore, dental caries may not have progressed to a degree that significantly affects aesthetics, which could explain the lack of a statistically significant impact on body image in this study.²²

Similarly, a systematic meta-analysis on oral health-related quality of life in children and adolescents, which included studies using the OIDP Questionnaire, found that the presence of dental

found that the presence of dental caries negatively affected adolescents' quality of life.²⁵

Since quality-of-life scales incorporate multidimensional aspects, including functional well-being, emotional well-being, and self-esteem, the negative impact of dental caries on quality of life does not necessarily imply a direct effect on body image. Given that dental caries is more commonly associated with oral health and functional concerns rather than aesthetics, the lack of a significant relationship between body image and dental caries in this study is a reasonable finding.

These findings indicate that body image is significantly associated with the need for orthodontic treatment but is not directly related to other dental health factors such as tooth loss and dental caries. The fact that orthodontic disorders are more closely linked to aesthetic concerns supports this result. However, it should be noted that factors such as age, social environment, and overall health status may influence the impact of tooth loss and dental caries on an individual's body image.²⁶

This study examined the relationship between RSES scores and the presence of orthodontic treatment needs, tooth loss, and dental caries. The findings indicate that there was no statistically significant relationship between self-esteem and these variables.

Self-esteem is influenced by how individuals perceive themselves and can be affected by various psychosocial and physical factors. While oral and dental health is known to play a role in physical appearance, social interactions, and overall psychosocial well-being, the present study found that orthodontic treatment needs did not have a significant impact on self-esteem ($p = 0.517$). This result is consistent with some previous studies. For example, a study by Johal et al.²⁷ found that individuals requiring orthodontic treatment did not necessarily have lower self-esteem but suggested that aesthetic concerns may vary based on individual differences. Similarly, Dann et al.²⁸ assessed self-concept in 208 individuals aged 7 to 15 years using the Pierre-Harris Self-Concept Scale and found no significant changes in self-concept scores during early treatment.

However, some longitudinal studies have suggested that orthodontic disorders may impact self-esteem, particularly in adolescents. Feu et al.¹⁹ reported that orthodontic treatment improved both oral health-related quality of life and self-esteem in adolescents over time. Additionally, a study by Perillo et al.⁵ found that orthodontic treatment need negatively affected self-esteem and self-perception in adolescents. Similarly, Badran²⁹ examined 385 adolescents aged 14–16 years and found that those who had undergone orthodontic treatment had higher self-esteem compared to those who had not. Furthermore, dissatisfaction with dental appearance was identified as a predictor of low self-esteem.

The contradictory findings in the literature may stem from the multifaceted nature of self-esteem, which is influenced by numerous factors beyond orthodontic treatment needs. Additionally, differences in sample demographics, age groups, and sociocultural backgrounds may contribute to variations in study results.³⁰

When examining the relationship between tooth loss and self-esteem, no significant difference was observed between individuals with and without missing teeth. Some studies suggest that tooth loss is associated with social isolation and decreased self-confidence, particularly in older individuals.²¹ This finding may be explained by the lower prevalence of tooth loss in the adolescent age group examined in this study, as compared to older populations. Additionally, some individuals may not perceive tooth loss as a significant aesthetic concern, and the availability of effective prosthetic solutions may further minimize its impact on self-esteem.

Similarly, no significant relationship was found between the presence of dental caries and self-esteem. The impact of dental caries on self-perception remains a debated topic in the literature.

While some studies suggest that dental caries negatively affects self-esteem³¹, others indicate that this relationship is not particularly strong.³² These contradictory findings in the literature may stem from differences in sample age groups, sociocultural factors, and variations in oral hygiene habits. Additionally, self-esteem is influenced by multiple factors, which may explain why a direct relationship between dental caries and self-esteem was not observed in this study.¹

These findings suggest that the degree to which individuals are affected by oral health-related physical factors varies based on personal, cultural, and socioeconomic factors. Additionally, self-esteem is a multidimensional construct and should not be viewed solely as physical appearance.¹ Future large-scale and longitudinal studies are recommended to further evaluate the relationships between these variables.

Studies on the impact of dental aesthetics on body image have shown that individuals with orthodontic issues tend to perceive themselves as less attractive and experience higher levels of social anxiety.³³ Malocclusion-related factors such as crowding, misalignment, and noticeable occlusal issues can reduce comfort in smiling and lead to increased self-consciousness in social settings.³⁴

This study provides valuable insights into the impact of orthodontic issues, tooth loss, and dental caries on body image and self-esteem. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study in the literature to examine the relationship between common dental anomalies and body image. Given that adolescence is a critical period for the development of self-esteem and body image, focusing on this age group enhances the significance of the study's findings. Furthermore, the study's sample size of 167 participants exceeds the typical sample size used in cross-sectional studies in this field, and the use of scientifically validated measurement tools strengthens its reliability.

Despite its strengths, this study has certain limitations. Its cross-sectional design makes it difficult to establish causal relationships between variables. Additionally, the study's narrow age range of 15–17 years limits the generalizability of the results to the broader population. Another limitation is that the assessment tools relied on self-reported data, and structured psychiatric evaluations were not conducted to identify potential comorbid psychiatric disorders. Future longitudinal studies incorporating structured psychiatric interviews across different age groups are necessary to provide a more comprehensive understanding of these relationships.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study suggests that while orthodontic treatment need negatively affects body image, tooth loss and dental caries may not have a significant impact on body image or self-esteem. Given the negative influence of orthodontic issues on body image, further research is needed to explore the relationship between oral health and psychological well-being. These findings emphasize that orthodontic treatments are not only important for aesthetic reasons but also play a crucial role in improving individuals' psychological well-being.

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The authors declare that no conflict of interest is available

Review Article

Antibacterial Efficacy of Chlorhexidine in Endodontic Treatments: A Systematic Review of Recent Evidence on Biofilm Inhibition and Clinical Outcomes

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Chlorhexidine, particularly at a 2% concentration, significantly reduces bacterial load and inflammatory markers in endodontic treatments. Optimized use improves periapical healing, making it an effective final irrigant while minimizing cytotoxic risks through

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This systematic review aims to evaluate the recent evidence on the antibacterial efficacy, biofilm inhibition, and clinical outcomes of chlorhexidine (CHX) in endodontic treatments. Recognized for its potent antimicrobial properties and minimal toxicity, CHX is widely utilized as an irrigant, yet its clinical benefits and potential cytotoxic effects require further exploration.

Materials and Methods: Following PRISMA guidelines, a comprehensive search was conducted in PubMed, focusing on studies published within the last three years. Nineteen studies meeting the inclusion criteria were analyzed. Data on CHX concentrations, application methods, and clinical outcomes were extracted, and the findings were categorized based on diagnoses, concentrations used, and effects observed.

Results: Among the included studies, 63% investigated CHX as a standalone irrigant, while 37% assessed its combination with other solutions. The most commonly used concentration was 2%, demonstrating significant efficacy in reducing bacterial loads and inflammatory markers, particularly in apical and asymptomatic apical periodontitis. As a final irrigant, CHX effectively reduced *E. faecalis* and lipopolysaccharide levels, promoting periapical healing. However, 0.12% CHX showed limited efficacy and cytotoxic effects, especially on periodontal ligament fibroblasts. Studies highlighted concerns about cytotoxicity and tissue solubility, emphasizing the importance of concentration optimization.

Conclusion: Chlorhexidine, especially at a 2% concentration, is effective in endodontic treatments, offering antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory benefits. Careful application protocols are essential to minimize cytotoxic risks. Further research is needed to refine its clinical use and establish standardized guidelines.

1. Introduction

Chlorhexidine has been identified as a highly effective endodontic agent, recognized for its broad-spectrum antibacterial properties and minimal toxicity. These attributes, along with its lack of tissue-dissolving capabilities, underscore its significance in endodontic applications. Notably, chlorhexidine exhibits antimicrobial effects comparable to sodium hypochlorite in endodontic procedures.¹ Furthermore, its sustained antimicrobial activity post-application significantly reduces intra-canal microbial flora, making it a valuable asset in endodontic practice.^{2,3}

In addition to its use as an irrigant, chlorhexidine has found application in various aspects of endodontic treatment. It is commonly employed in endodontic re-treatment procedures, particularly as a final irrigant to eliminate resistant microorganisms such as *Enterococcus faecalis*.¹ Furthermore, chlorhexidine is sometimes combined with calcium hydroxide as an intracanal medicament to enhance periapical healing. Its prolonged antimicrobial effect, even after application, helps in reducing the microbial load in persistent infections.²

Chlorhexidine plays a crucial role in maintaining the stability of dentin collagen fibrils during endodontic treatments. This is particularly relevant in preventing the degradation of the hybrid layer, which can be caused by enzymatic activity.⁴⁻⁷ By inhibiting matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), chlorhexidine preserves the integrity of the dentin bonding interface.⁷⁻⁹ Additionally, it can be applied alongside other bonding agents, ensuring stronger adhesion between composite materials and acid-etched enamel. This application supports both the durability of the adhesive bond and long-term treatment success.⁹⁻¹¹

The objective of this systematic review is to critically evaluate the recent literature on the use of chlorhexidine in endodontic treatments, focusing on studies published in the last three years. The review will systematically assess chlorhexidine's antibacterial efficacy, particularly in biofilm inhibition, and its clinical success at different concentration levels. This approach aims to synthesize current evidence and provide a comprehensive understanding of chlorhexidine's effectiveness as an irrigating solution, offering valuable insights for endodontic practitioners in clinical decision-making.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Guidance

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The PRISMA checklist was followed to ensure comprehensive reporting, including transparent study selection, data extraction, and analysis.

2.2. Search strategy

A systematic electronic search was conducted in PubMed, utilizing the keywords "chlorhexidine" and "endodontics treatment," while excluding terms such as "antibiotics" and "probiotics." The search was restricted to articles published in the last three years to ensure the inclusion of recent studies. No additional filters were applied beyond limiting the search to English-language studies. The screening process involved reviewing titles, abstracts, and full-texts to identify relevant studies for further analysis. The last search was conducted on 21.06.2024.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the study protocol

2.3. Eligibility Criteria

This review included studies that specifically examined the use of chlorhexidine as an irrigation solution during endodontic procedures. Articles were included if they were published in the last three years, written in English, and contained the keywords "chlorhexidine" and "endodontic treatment." Studies combining chlorhexidine with antibiotics or probiotics were considered eligible if the data focused on chlorhexidine's application within the pulp chamber or root canals. This review included original research and review articles that investigated the application of chlorhexidine in endodontic treatments. Studies such as case reports, and editorials were excluded to ensure the inclusion of primary data and clinical trials focusing on chlorhexidine's use as an irrigant.

2.4. Study Selection Process

Three independent reviewers (IR, MK, and KS) conducted the initial screening and analysis of the articles. The reviewers were familiarized with the study's objectives and applied predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Any disagreements during the selection process were discussed and resolved through consensus with the assistance of a fourth expert (SH) to ensure impartiality. The final selection of articles was determined collaboratively. A thorough screening and selection process was conducted to identify relevant studies for inclusion in this review. Initially, 15,501 records were identified from various databases. Of these, 14,623 records were removed by automation tools due to ineligibility, and 206 records were excluded for other reasons. This left 672 records to be screened. After screening, 534 records were excluded, and 138 reports were sought for retrieval. Unfortunately, 60 of these reports could not be retrieved.

Subsequently, 78 reports were assessed for eligibility. At this stage, 34 reports were excluded for Reason 1, 13 for Reason 2, and 12 for Reason 3, which could reflect methodological issues,

Table 1. Data on the type of articles included in the study presented depend on the indication of the application of chlorhexidine as a canal irrigant, undiluted as a solution by itself, or as combined with other irrigating solutions.

CHX	CHX-other irrigators
Karaoglan F et al. ²	Tonini R et al. ¹
Kichler V et al. ⁴	Jeong JW et al. ³
Rasaiah SR et al. ⁵	Gabrielli ES et al. ⁷
da Silva TA et al. ⁶	Corrazza BJM et al. ¹⁰
Minavi B et al. ⁸	Teixeira FFC et al. ¹⁶
Tandon J et al. ⁹	Godoi-Jr EP et al. ¹⁷
Eren SK et al. ¹¹	Martinho FC et al. ¹⁸
Teixeira FFC et al. ¹²	
Yao Y et al. ¹³	
Hajihassani N et al. ¹⁴	
Jose J et al. ¹⁵	
Kurt SM et al. ¹⁹	
12 articles – 63%	7 articles – 37%

incomplete data, or failure to meet specific criteria. Ultimately, 19 studies 1-19 met the inclusion criteria and were incorporated into the final review. This selection process demonstrates the rigorous approach used to ensure that only high-quality and relevant studies were included in the analysis (Fig.1).

2.5. Data Extraction

Data were extracted based on predefined criteria, including the method of chlorhexidine application (as a standalone irrigant or in combination with others), the specific endodontic diagnosis where chlorhexidine was indicated for root canal irrigation, and the concentration of chlorhexidine used. The extraction focused on identifying the most effective concentrations and their associated success rates, as reported in the selected studies.

2.6. Risk of Bias Assessment

Due to the wide range of included studies, spanning from clinical trials to in vitro studies, a formal risk of bias assessment using standardized criteria was deemed inappropriate. The variability in study designs and methodologies made it challenging to apply a uniform assessment tool. As a result, a risk of bias evaluation was not performed for this review.

3. Results

PRISMA diagram flow shows the process of selecting articles in a visual way shown in Figure 1. After analyzing the studies selected in this study, based on the selection criteria, data collection and processing are presented in the following tables. Table 1 shows the distribution of articles based on whether chlorhexidine is indicated to be used alone as a solution or in combination with other endodontic solutions during the irrigation process of the canal where it is applied. In the analysis of studies investigating the use of irrigants in endodontic treatment, a total of 19 articles were reviewed. Among these, 12 articles (63%) focused exclusively on the use of CHX as the primary irrigant. These studies, conducted over several years, assessed the effectiveness, and application of CHX in root canal treatments. In contrast, 7 articles (37%) explored the use of CHX in combination with other irrigators or compared

Table 2. The division of articles according to the in vivo, in vitro or review category and specific endodontic diagnoses. This classification method once again specifically shows the effect of chlorhexidine as an endodontic irrigant based on the type of study performed.

Type of study	In vivo	In vitro	Total
Endodontic diagnosis			
Apical Periodontitis	7 articles ^{7,9,10,12,13*,16,18} – 36%	2 articles ^{8,13*} – 11%	9 articles – 47%
Asymptomatic apical periodontitis	3 articles ^{2,6,19} – 16%	1 article ¹⁷ – 5%	4 articles – 21%
Symptomatic apical periodontitis	1 article ¹⁰ - 5%	-	1 article – 5%
No specific diagnosis	0 – 0%	5 articles ^{3,4,11,14,15} - 26%	5 articles – 26%
Total	11 articles – 58%	8 articles – 42%	19* – 100%

* This article has been mentioned twice since the analysis carried out in the study included in this article was carried out in parallel both in vivo in humans and in vitro for laboratory analysis of samples taken from oral cavities. Hence, the number of articles in total endodontic comes out at or 1 greater. The percentages were calculated from the total number of items from table no. 2.

it to alternative solutions.

Table 2 presents the articles based on the type of case report study, cross-sectional or retrospective of the in vivo category articles, divided according to specific endodontic diagnoses. The included studies were categorized based on their focus on different types of endodontic diagnoses and the methodology used. A total of 19 studies were analyzed, with 58% (11 studies) being in vivo, 42% (8 studies) in vitro, and 5% (1 study) as a review. The most commonly investigated condition was apical periodontitis, accounting for 47% of the studies, with 36% being in vivo and 11% in vitro. Asymptomatic apical periodontitis was the second most common diagnosis, with 21% of the studies, 16% of which were in vivo and 5% in vitro. Only 5% of the studies focused on symptomatic apical periodontitis, represented by a single in vivo study. Additionally, 32% of the studies did not specify a particular diagnosis, with 26% of these being in vitro and 5% being a review. This distribution highlights a stronger focus on apical periodontitis and a preference for in vivo studies across the included literature.

Table 3 shows data on the indicated proportion of chlorhexidine as an endodontic irrigant. The studies were categorized based on the concentration of CHX used and the type of endodontic diagnosis. Out of 19 total studies, the majority (84%) used 2% CHX, while only 10% used 0.12% CHX, and 5% did not specify the CHX concentration. Apical periodontitis was the most commonly studied condition, with 42% of the articles focusing on this diagnosis, all using 2% CHX. Similarly, 21% of the studies investigated asymptomatic apical periodontitis, with all of them also using 2% CHX. Symptomatic apical periodontitis was addressed in just 1 study (5%), which used 0.12% CHX. For studies with no specific diagnosis, 31% of the articles fell into this category, with a mix of CHX concentrations: 5% used 0.12%, 21% used 2%, and 5% did not specify. Overall, the data shows a clear preference for 2% CHX in the majority of the included studies, especially for apical and asymptomatic apical periodontitis.

Table 4 shows specifically the effects of chlorhexidine 0.12% classified as negative or positive effects, based on the data of the articles included in the analysis. The effects of 0.12% CHX were examined in two distinct endodontic contexts. In studies with no precise diagnosis, 0.12% CHX was found to have a negative effect due to its cytotoxicity against periodontal ligament fibroblasts. On the other hand, in cases of symptomatic apical periodontitis, 0.12% CHX demonstrated a positive effect by effectively reducing contamination during emergency pulpotomy, targeting microorganisms such as *S. epidermidis*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and fungi. Overall, the findings show an equal balance

Table 4. This table shows the data or conclusions of the articles included in the study classified as positive or negative effects of endodontic application of chlorhexidine 0.12%.

Effect of CHX diagnoses	0.12% Endodontic	Negative effect	Positive effect
No precise diagnosis	0.12% CHX	has cytotoxicity against periodontal fibroblasts. ⁽⁴⁾	-
Symptomatic apical periodontitis	-	-	Reduces contamination during emergency pulpotomy by acting on <i>S. epidermidis</i> , <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> and fung. ⁽⁵⁾
Results	1 article / 1article - rate 1:1		

between positive and negative effects, with one article reporting cytotoxic risks and another highlighting its antimicrobial benefits.

Table 5 shows all the articles that analyze the clinical effect of the application of chlorhexidine 2% during root canal treatments, classified as negative effects or positive clinical effects. The effects of 0.12% CHX as an endodontic irrigant were analyzed across various diagnoses, showing both positive and negative outcomes. For apical periodontitis, CHX had negative effects such as failing to reduce periapical inflammation markers and being less effective in reducing bacterial load across multiple species. However, its positive effects included reducing lipopolysaccharide levels, being highly effective against *E. faecalis*, and decreasing inflammation markers like IL-10, IL-17, and IL-21 after 14 days, making it a recommended final irrigant for endodontic re-treatments. In cases of asymptomatic apical periodontitis, while CHX did not contribute to periapical tissue healing and factors like gender and age influenced the prognosis, it was found to significantly reduce bacterial load, aiding in the healing of endodontic lesions. For symptomatic apical periodontitis, no effects—positive or negative—were reported.

In studies with no precise diagnosis, negative effects included CHX toxicity to human fibroblasts and interactions with heavy metals in irrigants, while positive effects included effectiveness against *E. faecalis*. Overall, with a ratio of 1:1.3 between negative and positive effects, 0.12% CHX demonstrated some cytotoxic risks but also showed strong antimicrobial properties, particularly in reducing inflammation and bacterial load in endodontic treatments.

Table 3. This table presents the data collected from the processing of the articles included in the study classified according to endodontic clinical diagnoses and the chlorhexidine solution that was taken in the study.

Percentage of diagnoses	CHX Endodontic	0.12%	2%	No % specified	Total
Apical Periodontitis	-	-	Gabrieli et al.2022 ⁷ Minavi et al.2021 ⁸ Tandon et al.2022 ⁹ Corazza BJM et al.2021 ¹⁰ Teixera FFC et al.2022 ¹² Yao Y et al.2021 ¹³ Teixeira FFC et al. 2022 ¹⁶ Martinho FC et al.2023 ¹⁸ – 8 articles 42%	-	8 – 42%
Asymtomatic apical periodontitis	-	-	Karaoglan F et al.2022 ² da Silva TA et al.2023 ⁶ Godoi-Jr Ep et al.2023 ¹⁷ Kurt SM et al.2022 ¹⁹ – 4 articles 21%	-	4 – 21%
Symptomatic apical periodontitis	Rasaiah et al. 2021 ⁵ – 1 article (5%)	-	-	-	1 – 5%
No specific diagnosis	Kichler et al. 2021 ⁴ - 1 artikull (5%)	-	Jeong JW et al. 2021 ³ Eren SK et al. 2022 ¹¹ Hajihassani N et al. 2022 ¹⁴ Jose J et al. 2021 ¹⁵ - 4 articles 21%	Tonini R et al. 2022 ¹ – 1 article 5%	6 – 31%
Total		2 articles– 10%	16 articles – 84%	1 article – 5%	19 – 100%

Table 5. Data collected from the articles included in the study based on the conclusions with positive effects or negative effects of the application of chlorhexidine as an endodontic irrigant.

Effect of 0.12% CHX Endodontic diagnoses	Negative effect	Positive effect
Apical periodontitis	CHX-Ca(OH) ₂ does not reduce PA inflammation markers, whereas N-acetylcysteine does. ¹⁰ CHX-Ca(OH) ₂ reduces the bacterial load in quantity but not in multiple species of bacteria. ¹⁸	Intracanal CHX-Ca(OH) ₂ reduces lipopolysaccharide but not lipoteichoic acid levels that cause clinical symptoms. ⁷ Effective from <i>E.faecalis</i> is even taken as a control unit for other equally effective solutions. ⁸ Superior effect to <i>E.faecalis</i> is recommended as a final irrigator for endodontic re-treatments. ⁹ CHX-Ca(OH) ₂ reduces the level of MMP1, MMP-2, MMP-9 after 14 days intra-canal. ¹² CHX is taken as a control for the effect against <i>E.faecalis</i> . ¹³ CHX-Ca(OH) ₂ decrease the level of IL-10, IL-17, IL-21 causing pain in percussion. ¹⁶
Asymptomatic apical periodontitis	Irrigation stops but does not affect periapical tissue healing. ² Gender and age influence as prognostic factors after application. ⁶	Significantly reduces the bacterial load in the root canals of teeth with indication for endodontic re-treatment. ¹⁷ Final rinse to aid in the healing of asymptomatic mandibular endodontic lesions. ¹⁹
Symptomatic apical periodontitis	-	-
No precise diagnosis	NaOCl-CHX toxicity not only to bacteria but also to human fibroblasts. ³ Irrigant that promotes tissue solubility and crystal precipitation. ¹¹ Endodontic sealants interact with heavy metals in irrigants at various incidences. ¹⁵	Effective against <i>E.faecalis</i> . ¹⁴
Results	7 articles / 9 articles - rate 1:1.3	

4. Discussion

This systematic review comprehensively evaluated the efficacy and usage trends of chlorhexidine in endodontic treatments. The majority of the reviewed studies highlighted the widespread use of chlorhexidine, particularly at a 2% concentration, in the treatment of apical periodontitis. Findings emphasize chlorhexidine's antibacterial properties and its effectiveness in reducing microbial load within root canals. However, negative effects such as cytotoxicity risks associated with chlorhexidine were also identified. This study contributes to a better understanding of chlorhexidine's potential positive and negative impacts on clinical success, elucidating its role in endodontic applications.

The data reviewed in this study indicate that the most commonly used concentration of chlorhexidine is 2%, particularly for endodontic diagnoses such as apical periodontitis.²⁰ This concentration is notable for its positive effects, such as reducing microbial load within root canals and controlling inflammatory markers.²¹ However, caution must be exercised, as the extrusion of 2% chlorhexidine into periapical tissues can lead to toxic effects.²² Conversely, 0.12% chlorhexidine demonstrated a negative profile in certain studies due to its cytotoxic impact on periodontal fibroblasts.²³ These findings underscore the need for careful clinical application of chlorhexidine, emphasizing the importance of optimizing its concentration based on specific treatment protocols.

The findings of this study support the efficacy of chlorhexidine in endodontic treatments while also highlighting significant limitations that must be considered in clinical applications. The effect of chlorhexidine is shown to vary greatly depending on the concentration used, the duration of application, and the type of tissue it interacts with.²⁴ Given the cytotoxic risks associated with lower concentrations and the potential toxic effects of higher concentrations, establishing appropriate application protocols is crucial. Moreover, further clinical studies are needed to determine whether chlorhexidine is more effective when used alone or in combination with other irrigants. Such research could play a critical role in enhancing the clinical success of chlorhexidine and maximizing patient safety.

Table 2 highlights that the largest proportion of articles on chlorhexidine as an endodontic irrigant focuses on specific endodontic diagnoses. This reflects the primary goal of initial endodontic treatments: the mechano-chemical removal of canal

biofilm, which can lead to apical periodontitis due to bacterial virulence factors. Several studies^{8,9,17} analyze the efficacy of chlorhexidine as a final irrigant for achieving clinical success in endodontic re-treatments. However, this data contrasts with the greater number of articles that evaluate chlorhexidine as the primary irrigant for asymptomatic apical periodontitis^{2,6,17,19}, comprising about 13%, compared to only 3% of articles addressing its use in symptomatic apical periodontitis.⁵ These studies assessed periapical lesions based on radiographic radiolucency changes. Notably, an *in vivo* study⁶ on asymptomatic apical periodontitis concluded that factors such as gender and age influenced the effectiveness of 2% chlorhexidine.

The fact that a significant portion of studies on the efficacy of chlorhexidine were conducted *in vivo* highlights its importance in evaluating the compound's effectiveness and safety in clinical settings. With *in vivo* studies comprising 34% of the articles, compared to 25% for *in vitro* studies, this discrepancy may point to some limitations in correlating laboratory findings with clinical practice. Data from Table 3 reveal that 2% chlorhexidine is the most frequently used concentration, particularly in specific endodontic pathologies such as apical periodontitis, underscoring its effectiveness in reducing bacterial load. However, the limited number of studies focusing on 0.12% chlorhexidine^{4,5}, especially in symptomatic apical periodontitis cases, suggests a narrower clinical application and possible concerns about cytotoxicity. These findings emphasize the need for careful selection of chlorhexidine concentrations and the development of tailored protocols for specific endodontic diagnoses in clinical practice.

The positive effects of 0.12% chlorhexidine outlined in Table 4 appear to hold less clinical significance compared to its negative effects. Although data is limited, it is clear that irrigation pressure with chlorhexidine, especially when used as a final rinse before endodontic canal filling, must be carefully controlled to avoid passage into the periodontal ligament. According to Table 5, the effectiveness of 2% chlorhexidine, measured as a ratio of negative to positive effects, stands at 1:1.3—indicating a somewhat inconclusive balance. Notably, one of the key negative effects is its potential to impede periapical tissue healing, emphasizing that its application should be restricted to the canal territory. On the positive side, 2% chlorhexidine shows a reduction in inflammatory markers at the periapical level and a significant decrease in bacterial flora, particularly *E. faecalis*, which is a major cause of endodontic treatment failure.

5. Conclusion

The clinical value of chlorhexidine as a periodontal irrigant is well-established due to its potent antimicrobial properties. Recent trends in scientific research have highlighted its potential in endodontic applications, where it combats periodontal bacterial flora that can extend to the periapex through the root canal system. Chlorhexidine demonstrates favorable clinical effects on periapical endodontic lesions and is often recommended as a final rinse before canal filling, including in cases of endodontic retreatments. Among the various concentrations, 2% chlorhexidine is the most commonly indicated for endodontic treatments due to its proven effectiveness in reducing bacterial load and controlling inflammation. However, careful attention must be paid to the irrigation technique and pressure during its application, as excessive force may lead to the solution's passage into the periodontal ligament, potentially causing undesirable effects. Therefore, optimizing the use of chlorhexidine by balancing its concentration and application protocol is crucial to maximizing its clinical benefits while minimizing risks.

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Data Availability Statement

The datasets analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author.

Ethics Approval

This study was approved by the Albanian University Institutional Ethics Committee (02.11.2023), Tirana, Albania, according to national regulations.

Conflict of Interest

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Case Report

Endodontic management of a maxillary first molar with seven root canals using a dental operating microscope: A case report

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Clinicians must have knowledge of the anatomical variations during all phases of endodontic diagnosis and treatment and should use advanced magnification or diagnostic techniques to help in the detection of such abnormalities and the eventual success of endodontic therapy.

ABSTRACT

The main objective of root canal treatment is the thorough cleaning and shaping of the entire root canal system. For this, the detection of all canals is of significant clinical importance. Maxillary first molars (Mx1M) commonly present with three roots and three canals, with a second mesiobuccal canal (MB2) also present. With the advent of improved diagnostic systems, it has been reported that Mx1M can have different anatomical variations. This varying number of configurations presents a challenge to the endodontist in detecting and treating through the root canal. This problem can be avoided by using magnification systems or advanced diagnostic techniques. Although four canals were detected at the beginning of the treatment, a rare morphology and three additional canals were detected with the contribution of a dental operating microscope (DOM). This case report presents the endodontic management of an Mx1M with pulpal necrosis and symptomatic apical periodontitis. Nonsurgical endodontic therapy of a left Mx1M with three roots and seven root canals was successfully performed under a DOM.

1. Introduction

The primary goals of conventional endodontic treatment are removing pulp tissue and irritants from root canals and hermetically sealing the canal system. Accurate diagnosis and detection of all root canals are crucial for success; otherwise, the root canal system cannot be fully cleaned and filled, leading to treatment failure.¹ Human maxillary first molars (Mx1M) typically have four or five cusps, three roots (mesiobuccal, distobuccal, and palatal), and four canals.² However, studies and case reports have revealed anatomical variations, including Mx1M with one, two, or five roots³⁻⁶ and three-rooted versions with multiple canals.⁷⁻⁹

This case report presents a rare Mx1M configuration with seven root canals: two mesiobuccal, three palatal, and two distobuccal, diagnosed during treatment. A thorough understanding of root canal morphology, proper clinical and radiographic examination, and the use of dental loupes or dental operating microscopes (DOM) are essential for success. This article highlights Mx1M morphological variations and additional canal management.

2. Case Presentation

An 18-year-old male patient presented to the Endodontics Department at Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University Faculty of Dentistry, Rize, Turkey, with a ten-day history of spontaneous and mastication-induced pain in the maxillary right posterior region. His medical history was unremarkable. He reported intermittent pain for two months, worsening in recent days. Clinical examination revealed a deep mesio-occlusal carious lesion, tender on percussion. Cold testing with Endo-Frost (Coltene, Switzerland) on tooth Mx1M was negative. Buccal and palatal palpation showed no tenderness, but vertical percussion was painful. Periodontal

probing and mobility were within physiological limits. A preoperative periapical radiograph showed a mesio-occlusal carious lesion close to the pulp and widening of the periodontal ligament space near the mesiobuccal root (Fig. 1A). Based on clinical and radiographic findings, pulpal necrosis with symptomatic apical periodontitis was diagnosed, and nonsurgical endodontic treatment was planned. After obtaining informed consent, root canal treatment was initiated.

Local anesthesia was administered using 1.8 mL of 2% articaine with 1:200,000 epinephrine (Haver Pharma; Septodont, Istanbul, Turkey). An access cavity was prepared under rubber dam isolation. After access, the mesiobuccal 1 (MB1), distobuccal 1 (DB1), and mesiopalatal (MP1) canal orifices were located. Upon detecting the second mesiobuccal (MB2) canal, additional canals were suspected. The procedure continued under a dental operating microscope (DOM) (Extaro 3000, Carl Zeiss Meditec, Germany) at 2.5× magnification (Fig. 2). Examination with the DOM revealed a second palatal canal (MP2) and a third palatal orifice (DP). A dentin aberrancy between DB and DP orifices suggested an extra canal, leading to the discovery of the second distobuccal (DB2) canal 3 mm buccally to DP with an ultrasonic tip (E4D, Woodpecker, China). Three additional canals (MP2, DP, DB2) were identified, necessitating modification of the traditional triangular access to a trapezoidal shape. Due to calcification, MB2 and DB2 required multiple attempts for exploration using ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and ISO #8 K-files (Mani, Japan). Patency was confirmed with ISO #10 K-files. Orifices were shaped using ProTaper Gold SX (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland) (Fig. 3). Working length was determined with an apex locator

Fig. 1. (A) Periapical radiograph of the right maxillary first molar, (B) Master cone radiograph, (C) Post-obturation radiograph, (D) 2 months follow up

(Root ZX Mini, Morita, Japan). Cleaning and shaping were performed with ProTaper Universal files using the crown-down technique. Palatal canals were prepared to size 40.04, others to 30.04, with nickel-titanium rotary instruments. Irrigation was done with 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl). After a master cone radiograph (Fig. 1B), final irrigation was performed. NaOCl was

ultrasonically activated (DTE S6, Woodpecker, China), followed by 17% EDTA for 1 min per canal. The canals were dried with absorbent paper points (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland). Obturation was completed with cold lateral compaction of gutta-percha and AH Plus resin sealer (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland). A final radiograph was taken to assess obturation quality (Fig. 1C). The tooth was restored with a posterior composite filling (Z100; 3M ESPE, USA). The patient reported no post-treatment discomfort and remained asymptomatic at the 2-month follow-up (Fig. 1D).

3. Discussion

A thorough understanding of Mx1M root canal morphology is crucial for endodontic success. Variations, especially in multi-rooted teeth, pose challenges, as removing pulp remnants, microorganisms, and toxins is essential. Extensive isthmuses, anastomoses, and inaccessible areas exist in all multi-rooted teeth.¹⁰ Numerous studies have investigated Mx1M morphology.^{3, 11-13} Typically, it has three roots and four canals, with MB2 reported in over 50% of cases.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Case reports have documented the presence of three canals in the mesial root of Mx1M as well.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Mx1M commonly has a broad buccolingual mesiobuccal root and a rounded or ovoid distobuccal root²⁰, explaining the higher incidence of multiple MB canals.³ In the study by Sert and Bayırlı, the prevalence of Mx1M DB2 canal in the Turkish population was reported as 1.6–9.5%.²¹ Mx1M with the DB3 canal has also been reported in the literature.^{8,19,22,23} The incidence of five and six canals is 2.25–2.4% and 0.319–0.88%, respectively.^{24,25} Cases with three canals in the palatal root are also uncommon.^{26,27}

Fig. 2. Dental operating microscope (DOM) (Extaro 3000, Carl Zeiss Meditec, Germany) that was used in the study

Fig. 3. Canal orifices after coronal shaping

Root canal complexity is a major challenge in endodontics. Magnification is key in overcoming this, with the endodontic microscope revolutionizing the field by offering 3x–30x magnification and superior illumination. It has significantly improved both surgical and conventional endodontic outcomes. Key advantages of magnification include enhanced visualization, improved ergonomics, and increased referral rates.²⁷ Buhley et al. found MB2 detection rates of 71.1% with a microscope, 62.5% with dental loupes, and 17.2% without magnification.²⁸ In our case, three initially invisible canals were detected using a microscope. Periapical radiographs and DOM-assisted treatment helped determine root canal anatomy, though they may not always suffice.

In the past decade, micro-CT has emerged as the gold standard for studying root canal morphology due to its high-resolution imaging. While it provides more detail than CBCT, it is not clinically applicable.²⁹ CBCT aids in identifying complex root canals but was not used in this study, a potential limitation. However, DOM enabled a detailed examination, adhering to the ALARA principle, though CBCT use may be justified in some cases.

4. Conclusion

This report serves to present to the dental practitioners the complexities in root canal morphologies that the maxillary first molars can exhibit. A clinician should have a thorough knowledge of all the diversities and should perform a careful examination of the floor of the pulp chamber with a DOM. Lack of knowledge about accurate anatomical configurations of the root canals may lead dentists to leave remaining necrotic tissue, toxic products, and microorganisms in untreated missing canals, resulting in unsuccessful endodontic treatment.

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Conflict of Interest

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